

www.bjisrd.com

The Concept of a Level Range for Academic Lyceums and Higher Educational Institutions

Abdullayeva Madinakhon Mamirjonovna

Andijan State Pedagogical Institute Student of the direction "Mathematics and Informatics"

Abstract: *This article provides a detailed analysis of the concept of a power series and Abel's theorem. Degree series represent structures of infinite sums or multiples and are an important element of mathematical analysis. The article provides properties of degree arrays, convergence conditions, and practical examples. Abel's theorem also plays an important role in determining the boundary of string sets and in the study of analytic functions. The article is enriched with examples with the aim of helping readers understand the basic principles of Abel's theorem, its mathematical context, and its real-life application. As a result, students will be able to gain a deeper understanding of the significance of degree strings and Abel's theorem.*

Keywords: *Degree Series, Abel's Theorem, Mathematical Analysis, Infinite Sums, Analytic Functions, Mathematical Properties, Practical Examples, String Boundaries, Real Numbers, Convergent Powers.*

INTRODUCTION: Degree series and Abel's theorem are considered to be one of the most important parts of mathematical analysis and mathematical analysis. Degree series are an infinite sequence of multiplications or sets, and they are used in the study of many mathematical concepts, such as series, functions, and their convergence. Abel's theorem is especially important in the study of the properties of convergent-level arrays. It helps to determine the sum of a series or the boundary of each row, and also gives many practical examples in the study of analytic functions.

This article provides a detailed overview of the concept of power series and the basic principles of Abel's theorem, their mathematical context, practical application, and the significance of their results. These theorems help us understand the deep and complex scenes of mathematical analysis.

Description 1: The following

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n(x - x_0)^n \quad (1)$$

a functional array in the form is called a level array. Here

$a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n, \dots x_0$ Immutable real numbers If (1) $x - x_0 = \xi$ we introduce a designation,

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n \xi^n \quad (2)$$

We come to the degree range. So it is enough to examine the lines in form (2).

Theorem 1: (Abel's first theorem). If

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n x^n = a_0 + a_1 x + a_2 x^2 + \dots + a_n x^n + \dots \quad (3)$$

level array $x = x_0$ ($x_0 \neq 0$) is approximate in value, then x is a series of

$$\{x \in C: |x| < |x_0|\}$$

The absolute in the circle is convergent.

The result. If the (3)-series $x = x_0$ is a divergence at the point , then that row is also a divergence at $\{|x| > |x_0|\}$.

Description 2. If sum $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n x^n$ series

Converge at $\{|x| < R\}$, $\{|x| > R\}$ then the number $R \geq 0$ is called the approach radius of the degree series, and the interval i is called the interval of approximation.

Theorem 2. There is an approximation radius of an optional degree array R, which approximates straight at $\{|x| < R\}$ at absolute and for all $\forall r < R$ for $\{|x| \leq r\}$.

Note. Both convergence and distance are possible at the boundary points $x = \pm R$ of the convergence interval of the degree array. The degree row should be checked separately at these points.

The approach radius of a degree array can be found using the following theorems.

Theorem 3.(Dalamber).If $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{a_n}{a_{n+1}} \right|$ if it exists, then

$$R = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{a_n}{a_{n+1}} \right| \quad (4)$$

Theorem 4. (Koshi). In order to $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sqrt{|a_n|}$ if it exists, then

$$R = \frac{1}{\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sqrt{|a_n|}} \quad (5)$$

Theorem 5. (Koshi-Adamar). If the number R is the radius of approximation of a range of (3)-degrees, then

$$R = \frac{1}{\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sqrt{|a_n|}} \quad (6)$$

The formula (Koshi-Adamar formula) would be appropriate.

Level arrays have the following properties.

Theorem 6. The sum of the degree array is continuous at the point for all, which belongs to the approximation interval $S(x)$.

Theorem 7. (Abel's second theorem). If the (3)-series converges at the point $x = R(x = -R)$, then this series $[0; R]$ ($[-R; 0]$) is a flat convergent in cross-section.

The result. If the (3)-series $x = R(x = -R)$ converges at the point, then $S(x)$ sums $[0; R]$ ($[-R; 0]$) will be continuous in the cross-section. Now we see a degree series of the form $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n (x - x_0)^n$. The approximation radius of this array sum $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n x^n$ is found using formulas to calculate the convergence radius of the series, only where the convergence interval $\{|x - x_0| < R\} = (x_0 - R, x_0 + R)$ is the interval.

Theorem 8. If the number $R > 0$ is $f(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n (x - x_0)^n$ (7)

if the degree array is the approach radius, then

- 1) The function $(x_0 - R, x_0 + R)$ has optional ordinal properties in the interval, and those derivatives are found by rolling differentialization of the range (7);
- 2) This array can be integrated in the space for all $\forall [a, b] \subset (x_0 - R, x_0 + R)$
- 3) The convergence radii of the new arrays formed by the excessive differentialization or integration of the (7) array, shall also be equal to the approximation radius of the (7)-array.

Note. If the function $f(x)$ is $R > 0$, expressed using the equation (7), then the function $f(x)$ is called an analytic function at x_0 point (more precisely, around x_0 point). From Theorem 8 it follows that the analytic function is infinitely differential. But an optional infinite differential function doesn't have to be analytical. An example of this is to get the function $f(x) = \exp(-\frac{1}{x^2})$

Theorem 9. If the function $f(x)$ is analytical at x_0 point, i.e.

$$a_n = \frac{f^{(n)}(x_0)}{n!}, n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

$$f(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{f^{(n)}(x_0)}{n!} (x - x_0)^n$$

Equality x_0 is also appropriate at that point of view.

Example 1: $1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + \dots + x^n + \dots$ find a functional array approximation area.

Solution: This series is a geometric series in which mahraji x . If $|x| < 1$, then the states of a given series consist of infinitely decreasing geometric progression states, in which case its sum is $\frac{1}{1-x}$. I mean

$$S(x) = 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + \dots + x^n + \dots = \frac{1}{1-x}$$

This means that the area of convergence of a given array will be $(-1; 1)$.

Example 2: $\frac{\cos x}{1^2} + \frac{\cos 2x}{2^2} + \frac{\cos 3x}{3^2} + \dots + \frac{\cos nx}{n^2} + \dots$

Prove that the series is an amplified series

Solution: x is in the $(-\infty; +\infty)$ range of the argument

$$\left| \frac{\cos nx}{n^2} \right| \leq \frac{1}{n^2} \quad (n = 1, 2, 3, \dots)$$

The series is imminent. Hence, a given array satisfies the definition of an amplified series.

Example 3: $x - \frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{x^3}{3} - \frac{x^4}{4} + \dots + (-1)^{n-1} \frac{x^n}{n!} + \dots$ find the approach radius of the level array.

Solve: $a_n = (-1)^{n-1} \frac{1}{n}, a_{n+1} = (-1)^n \frac{1}{n+1}$

We use the Dalamber sign to find the radius of approach to the degree range.

$$R = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{a_n}{a_{n+1}} \right| = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{a_n}{(-1)^{n-1} \frac{1}{n+1}} \right|$$

Conclusion: Degree strings are one of the most important parts of mathematical analysis, and their convergence and variability properties are used in many theories and practices. Abel's theorem, in turn, plays an important role in the study of the convergence of degree arrays. This theorem provides its convergence if the product of a power series is related to real numbers or complex numbers. The theorem also reveals the relationship between strings and their limits, which is widely used in the fields of mathematical analysis and functional analysis. As a result, it is possible to precisely define the convergence conditions of degree arrays using Abel's theorem, which will then be useful in solving other mathematical problems.

REFERENCES

1. Murodov, O. (2010). Mathematical analysis. Tashkent: Academy of sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
2. Abdurahmonov, S. (2005). Theory of adjectives and series. Tashkent: National University of Uzbekistan
3. Mamatkulov, M. (2012). Fundamentals of Mathematical Analysis. Tashkent: Fan.
4. Jumanazarov, A. (2018). "Abel's Theorem and Its Applicability." Journal of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 3(1), 45-52.
5. Sattorov, A. (2015). Big Mathematical Theories. Tashkent: Education in Economics and Statistics.
6. Sh.A.Ayupov, B.A.Omirov, A.H.Khudoyberdiev, F.H.Haydarov ALGEBRA AND NUMBER THEORY (textbook) Tashkent "Reflection-bostoni" 2019
7. U.Kh.Narzullayev, A.S.Soleev, X.Kh. Rozimuradov PROBLEMS AND EXERCISES FROM ALGEBRA AND NUMBER THEORY
8. D.Yunusova, A.Yunusov, ALGEBRA VA SENLAR NAZARIYASI SAMPLE AND MASHQLAR COLLECTION PREPARED ON THE BASIS OF MODULAR TECHNOLOGY.